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Research Article

**THE EFFECTS OF HEREDITY AND ENVIRONMENT ON THE
DEVELOPMENT OF THE HUMAN PERSONALITY OF THE
QURAN, SADI AND NEW PSYCHOLOGY**¹Kamal Gholami Amiralmomenin and ^{2*}Dr.Morteza Keshavarz¹Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch Islamic Azad University, Arsanjan Iran^{2*}Department of Psychology, Arsanjan Branch Islamic Azad University, Arsanjan Iran**Abstract**

Experts say that genetics and the environment are two factors that influence the human personality psychology. Some scholars believed that the evolution of human personality was due to the influence of genetic factors. Others believed that human personality strongly influenced the environment. Today, this belief has become more accepted, which is the formation of personality due to both factors of the environment and genetics. This theory is known as the effect of the gene-environment interaction (E×G or the theory of nature and education). Traits passed through human inheritance are a substrate that sometimes is reinforced by environmental factors such as education, and sometimes weakened. In addition, the person's will and determination also have a lot to do with his fate. The results of this study showed that all three perspectives of Holy Quran, Sadi and modern psychology, both factors of heredity and environment are effective in the development of human personality, and they argue that these two factors interact with each other to improve or weaken the personality in different people Gets.

Keywords: *psychology, holy Quran, saadi, character, heredity, environment***Corresponding author:**

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INTRODUCTION:

The personality of each human being is shaped by numerous and numerous factors, which leads to the type of person's thoughts and actions and behaviors. Perhaps the personality could include all human thoughts, states and behaviors. There is no doubt that there is personality as much as all human beings on earth. Each person has a special personality and behaves completely uniquely.

The most important factors that cause the formation of any human being, whether physical, mental or mental, are heredity and environment factors. Since the interstitial genes have been formed, the genes, which are the agents of the transfer of various genetic features, begin. Genes characterize all human characteristics. Features such as eye color and hairs color, height, face shape, skin color, heart size, etc. are some of the things. Whose inheritance plays a key role in them. So the type and form of the organs of the body, both externally and internally, are transmitted through the genes. But a number of scientists believe that although the heredity factor is important and important, one should never ignore another factor called the environment because it is an environment that, if desired, is effective in heredity and can cause the growth and development of genetic features to make For example, the shape and form of a person's body have the ideal genetic make-up. If there is no proper nutrition and environmental conditions, heredity will not be able to provide these specifications in full. Environmental conditions can be effective in maximizing the inherent characteristics of individuals [1].

Problem Statement and the Need for Research

One of the most important and controversial issues in various human disciplines is the personality debate that has led to various opinions and opinions from the views and schools of the school and the conflicts in various fields of science. In psychology, however, psychologists have not yet succeeded in defining the concept that everyone agrees with, and theories about personality and the quality of its formation in different schools, such as Freud's psychoanalytic behaviorism and humanistic psychology, are not the same. So personality definitions are abundant.

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behaviorism and humanistic psychology, are not the same. So personality definitions are abundant. One of the issues that characterize personality psychology is the emphasis on individual differences and the growth of unique attributes that have brought about the growth of human beings. Typically, the determinants of personality are divided into two groups of inherited and environmental determinants, the same as nature and education. That nature implies the role of genes in human personality and education on the role of the environment. Hereditary factors have a major role in determining personality, and this is especially true in the characteristics that are specific to each person [2-5] quoted by Parvin and John, 2002). Although many psychologists have emphasized the importance of environmental and heritable factors in the formation of personality during the history of psychology, recent theories believe that the importance of these factors varies in the personality traits of different individuals. For example, the importance of inherited factors in features such as intelligence and temperament is greater than in values, ideals and beliefs. One of the obvious examples of individual differences in mood, activity, and cowardice [6]. The personality of every human being is what shapes and directs his behavior. Perhaps this can be considered a general definition of personality from the perspective of the Quran. Understanding this definition can only be understood by understanding the elements that make up the personality in terms of the Quran. This definition shows that the person has a coherent and general structure, a structure that crystallizes in person's behavior. Therefore, the Quran, according to verse 84 of Sura al-Asra The personality of man is the one that shapes his behavior in the sense that the person has a coherent and general structure, a structure that crystallizes in his behavior [7]. In the Qur'an of Majid, the personality of man is expressed in a way that is distinct from animals, and human beings are not considered to be solely because of their physical characteristics, but to those with psychological characteristics It introduces a personality [8].

Research method

The research method is based on content analysis. Content analysis is a way to systematically and objectively deduce specific features of a text in order to provide a descriptive analysis and to present reality in a level or depth, or causal analysis, and the like Beheshti, 2007.

Information gathering method

The information gathering in this research will be through library resources and in accordance with the following steps:

- 1) Data collection, 2) information classification, 3) information analysis, and 4) inference of results

Information gathering tool

Fingerprinting and using databases and libraries and magazines and internet sites.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In this research, inferential analytical method (content analysis) will be used. There are a lot of definitions of content analysis method. Walliser and Weiner 1978, Defines content analysis as a regular method used to check the content of the recorded information [9]. In this way, messages or information are coded and categorized on a regular basis. The main goal is to analyze the content, to answer the questions that are directly related to the materials being analyzed (Delavare, 2011). Content analysis method

(Fred N. Kerlinger) provides a comprehensive description of this method: "Content analysis is a method of studying and analyzing relationships in a systematic, objective, and quantitative way to measure variables." He explains in the content analysis features: "In the past, this method has been less used to measure variables. But its new and increasing use in behavioral research has been to measure variables that were not possible to measure without this method. In this method, instead of directly observing the behavior of individuals or asking them to respond to scales or interview them, the researcher selects the relationships that individuals have created and questions them. "

Theories

Inheritance from the perspective of the Quran affects the development of human personality.

The environment from the perspective of the Quran affects the development of human personality.

Heredity and environment from the viewpoint of the Qur'an interact with the development of human personality.

Results

Hypothesis 1: Inheritance from the perspective of the Quran affects the development of human personality
Since the Holy Qur'an invites man to think and contemplate the way in which he was created, in the meantime, after passing through the stages of birth to death, he possesses a series of trait and vermin, some of which Inherits inheritance from his parents, and others recognize these traits after birth and during different stages of their development, and their goodness, and their good and bad distinguishes them from each other.

How can inheritance be effective in determining human personality?

- 1- In Maryam Surah, verses 27 and 28, the people of Maryam, marveled at his childhood, and said to him: "Your parents who have not been evil" here, the above verses indicate that the root of

one's moral virtues and vices Should be found in her parents.

- 2- 2- In Surah Noah, verses 26 and 27, in these verses, good attributes are passed from generation to generation.

Second hypothesis: The environment from the perspective of the Quran affects the development of human personality

The environment in the word is what surrounds the living being, and generally refers to external factors and forces that can be effective in its behavior. The environment generally consists of two parts of the pre-natal environment and the post-birth environment, and the postnatal environment itself includes the natural and geographical environment and the human and social environment. The major and important part that has a greater impact on the personality of people is the human and social environment that is created by the communication and interaction of individuals with each other. Like family, friends and peers, school, culture ... among which the family is more important [10].

The impact of the environment and nature on human personality has been very much considered, and the secret of this attention can be seen in matters such as the undeniable impact of the environment, and social factors in human body and soul. In Islamic texts, the impact of nature and environment on human personality is spoken differently. We read in the Qur'an as follows:

The clean and desirable land brings her crops to the permission of good God and leaves the land unfavorable except a small, fruitless and fruitless plant. "

Based on this, Amir al-Muminin Ali (as) says in reminders from Basra:

"Your morals, your posts, your treaties, your loose, sire, and your dreams, and the water of your city are a bitter taste."

Human education and social and environmental factors affecting behavioral personality play a very important role in creating a healthy person in the community. The behavioral characteristic of healthy personality holders in the Qur'an's view is so beautiful that the pattern for all humans is at all times and places. Therefore, in connection with the healthy environment, this verse clearly indicates: "Was not the earth of God vast enough to emigrate to it?" (Surah Nesaa, verse 97). Human beings evolve under the influence of natural factors, especially the region in which they live. These factors have a particular effect on the body and the spirit; for example, people who grow up in cold, warm, or temperate regions are

physically and psychologically different from others due to the climate differences in these areas.

Hypothesis 3: Heredity and the environment from the perspective of the Quran interact with the development of human personality

In the Qur'an, man is a special creature with a body of mud and godly spirit. On the one hand, in the presence of man, the divine spirit and nature of the Godhead, which can direct the divine direct guidance and identify the good and evil principles. On the other hand, the stretching of the body and in the Qur'an is the breath of the soul, some of which are put by God forghan (43) and Jasieh (23), there are those who set the divine orders as the light of their way They put up with devious commands (SuraNazeat, verse 43).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

The personality is such a complex phenomenon that has engulfed researchers over the past decades. Some scholars believed that the evolution of human personality was due to the influence of genetic factors. Others believed that human personality strongly influenced the environment. Today, this belief has become more accepted, which is the formation of personality due to both factors of the environment and genetics. This theory is known as the effect of the gene-environment interaction ($G \times E$ or the theory of nature and education). With the advent of new molecular and quantitative genetic branches that have greatly contributed to genetic behavior in the way of studying the effect of these two factors on behavior, the heredity of some human behaviors has already been recognized (Akrami et al., 2012). In order to examine the impact of the environment and inheritance on human personality, the issue of arbitrariness and arbitrariness is raised. Algebra and opulence in terms of psychology, as in other topics in other sciences, are about whether one has the ability to make decisions in his or her work. In other words, the purpose of empowerment here is a particular psychological ability of a person, on the basis of which he can dominate in particular territory, biological and environmental influences, and by choosing to choose his own behavior and course of his development consciously. Algebra is opposed in terms of meaning (Motvaseli, 2005). As the healthy climate of the environment affects the taste and taste of fruit trees and the color of the face, it also affects morality, customs and education, and it is clear that inheritance and the environment have a profound effect on humans. And he moves him towards the environment. The child, from the age of three to the character of the fixation, affects more than any period of the environment, as in linguistic dialects, functions, customs and habits ... It can be seen,

therefore, that the healthy environment of the human body is healthy, demonstrates the effect of healthy environment in a healthy person. The response of geneticists to the question of whether the fate of humans in his / her women has been coded is negative, noting that the identical twins are not alike in terms of form and behavior with the same genetic set, and this phenomenon suggests that human specification is influenced by a factor other than genetics. Most genes affect the environment to some extent. Therefore, the genes received from parents during fertilization do not exactly dictate our traits and characteristics (Alberts et al., 2008, p. 693). Human Behavioral Characteristics are a mixture of the effects of inheritance and the environment, and, in the meantime, one should not neglect the role of will and discretion. This is the truth that genetic science recognizes. Therefore, the existence of genetic factors in some undesirable ethical and behavioral attributes does not mean the issuance of permits for action, because who ultimately decides how to behave is a person himself. In order to determine the place of inheritance and environment in the person's destiny and personality from the point of view of the Quran and narratives, first the role of inheritance in shaping the traits and moral and moral characteristics are expressed, then the effect of inheritance on the fate is proved to be necessary, and finally, to The role of education and authority in the fate of man as two components affecting inherited traits is discussed. The Holy Qur'an calls for a person to think and contemplate and how to create it. Meanwhile, after passing through a series of births to death, a man possesses a series of trait and vermin, some of which are inherited He inherits from his parents, and some of them trace their traits after birth and during different stages of growth to their good and their adornment and distinguish them well and badly from each other. The Holy Qur'an, which is the most complete scripture and the word of God, also speaks of the interaction of the two factors of the environment and inheritance in the development of human personality:

(Brothers) said: If he (Benjamin) steals, (not surprisingly) because his brother (Yusuf) also robbed him before him ... "(Surah Yusuf, verse 77);" The prophets of this saying are the same as the paternal brothers Joseph, and for this reason, they attributed Joseph to Benjamin, saying that if Benjamin had stolen the king's throne today, he would not be surprised, and he would not be unbelievable, because he had a brother who had already committed theft and such a deed also flooded with him. So these two brothers inherited the robbery from their motherland, and we are separated from the motherland "(Tabatabai, 1417 Q.J., p. 236). From the perspective

of the Holy Quran, parents, in addition to interfering in the fate and character of their children through inheritance, are the cause of their child's happiness or adversity due to the great influence they have on his education. The Holy Quran says: "O you who believe, keep yourselves and your family from the fire which is the fire of those people and the rocks ..." (Surah al-Tahrim, verse 6). The verse reminds the believers about the importance of educating and getting into a hell of a fate. The maintenance of the family through education, the practice of good and forbidding, and the provision of a clean and free environment of any kind of pollution in the home and the family is realized. In other words, the right of women and children is not achieved only by the cost of living and housing and their nutrition. More important is feeding their souls and their lives and applying the principles of proper education (MakaremShirazi, 1995, p. 24: p. 286).

The Holy Qur'an says elsewhere, in relation to algebra:

(And gave you freedom and authority); some of you disbelievers and a believer ... "And he says: (and know) as you created at the beginning (again at the resurrection). * A collective And a group (who did not deserve) has been misled on them ... "(Surah A'raf, verse 29-30). This research showed that traits and moral characteristics (personality) transmitted through human inheritance are a substrate that sometimes is reinforced by environmental factors such as education, and sometimes weakened, In addition, the person's will and authority also have a lot to do with his fate. What a baby brings to this world as a living companion is the good and evil of being transmitted through the genes, but what affects her happiness and her wrath is not exclusive to heredity and the component Others, such as education and will, also have a significant impact on the fate of their fate, or even can sometimes overlap the inheritance law.

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